

How Soil Health Can be Improved by Agroforestry on Irish Farms

www.af4eu.eu

Soil profile of an agroforestry plot (photo TEAGASC)
Typical soil profile for a forestry site- with organic and underlying gley layers

References
MO'Brien, L., & Ni Dhubháin, Á. (2022). The role of agroforestry in improving soil health and mitigating climate change in Ireland. *Irish Forestry*, 79(2), 45-60.
Smith, J., Pearce, B., & Wolfe, M. (2018). Agroforestry: Enhancing soil function and biodiversity in European farming systems. *Agroforestry Systems*, 92(1), 1-14.

John Casey

Teagasc- the Agriculture and Food Development Authority, Ireland

Agroforestry in *Ireland* enhances soil health by improving structure, fertility, and resilience while addressing compaction, erosion, and nutrient loss. With high rainfall and sometimes fragile soils, integrating trees into farming systems boosts water infiltration and aeration, reducing compaction from livestock and machinery. Tree roots stabilize soil, preventing erosion, while leaf litter and root turnover enrich fertility. Nitrogen-fixing trees like alder naturally restore soil nutrients, reducing synthetic fertilizers and nutrient runoff, protecting water quality.

Agroforestry fosters biodiversity, promoting fungi, bacteria, and earthworms that enhance soil structure and nutrient cycling. Mycorrhizal fungi improve nutrient absorption and soil stability, strengthening farm resilience. Carbon sequestration is another key benefit, as trees store atmospheric CO₂ in their biomass and soil, enhancing soil carbon levels, water retention, and fertility, and contributing to climate change mitigation.

Silvopasture, where woody perennials and livestock coexist, reduces compaction, enhances pasture quality, and provides animal shelter. Other systems, like alley cropping (trees and crops) and riparian buffer zones (tree planting along waterways), control erosion and protect water resources. Challenges include potential soil compaction from overgrazing, particularly in wet conditions, and requires careful rotational grazing and tree placement. Ireland's naturally acidic soils necessitate strategic species selection, with oak, ash, alder, and hazel being common choices for improving soil health.

Agroforestry, supported by establishment grants (€6,000-€8,555) and 10-year annual premiums (€829- €975) from the *Department of Agriculture, Food, Fisheries and the Marine (DAFFM)*, presents a sustainable path for Irish agriculture, balancing productivity with conservation. By enhancing soil structure, biodiversity, and carbon storage, it ensures long-term resilience against climate change while preserving environmental health.

**Funded by
the European Union**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No GA 101086563. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.